

4. Article III. Exploring the jazz festival experience amongst local and non-local residents: The case of the Jazzaldia Festival in Spain

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Abstract

- **Purpose** The purpose of this paper is to explore the jazz festival experience at the Heineken Jazzaldia Festival in San Sebastian, Spain. It focuses especially on the relationship between participants' area of residence and their experience of the festival, concert expectations, preference for different festival settings, and perception of the best aspects of the festival.
- **Design/methodology/approach** This study modifies and applies the Audience Experience Survey (Radbourne et al., 2009) to the Heineken Jazzaldia Festival in San Sebastian, Spain. A total of 406 valid questionnaires were obtained. A quantitative analysis technique was used for the area of residence, on the one hand, and for concert expectations, audience experience, and venue setting, on the other. A qualitative approach was applied for identifying the best aspects of the festival.
- **Findings** The results suggest that the audiences' festival preferences differed according to their area of residence. Audience members who lived in Spain outside of the Basque Country were more motivated to attend the festival, had higher concert expectations and greater indoor venue concert attendance, and considered music diversity to be one of the most important aspects of the festival. Local participants were more likely not to have expectations prior to concerts, had higher outdoor venue concert attendance rates and preferred ambience, compared with residents from outside of the Basque Country.
- **Originality** This paper contributes to the literature regarding residents' behaviour in the Spanish music festival context. Our findings add to the body of knowledge around local audiences' and non-local audience's experience in jazz festivals.
- **Practical implications** Findings could be relevant to festivals' organisers for management and marketing purposes in terms of their audiences' needs and preferences. One of the main results obtained is that local residents were more likely not to have expectations prior to concerts. They also equalised music diversity, artists, stages, and atmosphere as the best Festival's aspects while participants from outside of Basque Country prioritised music diversity aspect.

Keywords: jazz, festival, area of residence, audience experience

4.1 Introduction

In recent years, the experience of music audiences has been addressed by a broad range of academic research. It has also been a focus for practitioners' initiatives in many international projects carried out by cultural institutions, associations, and researchers, such as ADESTE+ (www.adesteplus.eu), CONNECT (www.connectingaudiences.eu), and CULTUREHIVE (www.culturehive.co.uk). The effects of festivals on communities, audiences' motivations and behaviour, management key success factors, and market segmentation have been among the main subjects of study. Mair and Withford (2013) carried out a literature review on trends in event research and identified some aspects that need further academic attention. These included an analysis of attendees' motivations and behaviour, and of the socio-cultural and community impact. This may be reflected in areas such as residents' attitudes, social inclusion and capital, and a sense of community pride. This paper seeks to bridge the existing gap and contribute to the body of knowledge about the jazz festival audience experience, by exploring how it changes depending on the participants' area of residence. This paper has a specific regional impact as the audiences from San Sebastian, the rest of the Basque Country and Spain have been investigated. The underlying hypothesis is that the jazz festival experience of local residents differs from that of non-locals. Testing this hypothesis is relevant not only from a theoretical perspective, but also from a managerial viewpoint, as jazz festival managers could use the findings to facilitate more impactful audience experiences depending on the different targets. However, to do so, acknowledging that the audience experience from locals and non-locals is different is not enough and the differences should be further explored. To the best of our knowledge there has not been

carried out a research in the Spanish jazz festival context that focuses on this aspect. Therefore, this paper delves into this question, considering the specific case of Heineken Jazzaldia in Spain. A research carried out by Díez Mintegui and García Hernández (2010) recognises the Jazzaldia festival as an established cultural event in the city of San Sebastián, its autonomous community (Basque Country) and the whole country (Spain). However, their research has not identified differences in experiences among attendees in terms of their residence area. Therefore, this paper aims to shed light on this matter. To analyse the audience experience, the Audience Experience Survey for the performing arts (Radbourne et al., 2009; Radbourne et al., 2010) was modified and adapted to the jazz festival context. As the Survey originally did not include an item about the residence area, it had not been previously tested among local residents and tourists. An additional novel item that was included to the original Survey was the one capturing the perception of the audience in relation to the best aspects of the festival. We were particularly interested in exploring the relationship between the participants' area of residence and their experience of the festival, concert expectations, preference for different festival settings (outdoor versus indoor venues), and perception of the best aspects of the festival.

Founded in 1966, the Heineken Jazzaldia Festival² is one of the oldest jazz festivals in Europe. The Jazzaldia Festival has been characterised by live jazz music performed outdoors (at Plaza Trinidad in San Sebastian) ever since it was first held in 1966 (jazzaldia.eus, March 2021). This five-day festival currently features both indoor and

² As the fieldwork for this research was carried out in 2019, the festival was at that time called Heineken Jazzaldia. Today, Heineken is no longer the festival's main sponsor, and the festival is called Donostiako Jazzaldia (San Sebastián Jazz Festival).

outdoor stages, and free admission concerts. Its stages are integrated into the city's environment, and some of the stages are either on the beach or next to it.

4.2 Literature review

Festivals are a very important part of the jazz world, as they have a significant political, economic, and environmental impact on the communities involved (Webster and McKay, 2015). One of the characteristics of a jazz festival is that it brings together many different sounds and styles (Laver, 2015). It is precisely this richness of styles and the different cultural and creative influences that have a beneficial impact on cultural tourism and on the image of a place. Therefore, it is not surprising that jazz festivals are held in many different areas around the world (Li and Lin, 2016).

The importance that jazz festivals have can be seen through the academic efforts to reveal the influence they have on audiences, communities, and people's experiences. Jazz festival and audiences have been explored according to market segmentation (Kruger and Saayman 2013; Kruger and Saayman 2017; Thrane, 2002), economic impact (Bracalente et al., 2011; Brown, Var and Lee, 2002, Vecco and Srakar, 2017), place image (Curtis, 2010; Van Aalst and Van Melik, 2012), and management practices (Luonila and Johansson, 2016; Tkaczynski and Stokes, 2010). Drawing from the history of (European) jazz festivals, George McKay (2018) recalled their complex nature in terms of novelty, and a fluid aspect which is visible worldwide. Bonneau and Parantika (2016) underlined their cosmopolitan and sociable nature for both residents and tourists, as well as the way in which these festivals are able to influence the image of the city where they take place.

Barnés (2007) gave some insights into the Basque jazz music scene and stressed that festivals not only target jazz fans but also seek to attract general audiences. Moreover, when the Jazzaldia Festival was held for the second time (in 1967), it incorporated a new feature: presenting jazz music in the streets (Barnés, 2007). It is more than a festival, it is the City's festival (Díez Mintegui and Hernández García, 2010). Whyton (2018) held that, by enabling both a fresh relationship with local communities and their history, and a collaboration with local stakeholders and heritage sites, jazz festivals can become facilitators of extraordinary audience experiences.

Oakes and Warnaby (2011) researched outdoor venues in the jazz festival context and highlighted three continuums: managed/spontaneous, exclusive/inclusive, and spectacular/mundane. The first refers to the spontaneous atmosphere and the fact that audiences can freely move outdoors in comparison with organised management practices. Regarding the second continuum, outdoors spaces are more inclusive in terms of the audience's demographic profile and have no reserved seats, unlike indoor venues. The third continuum encompasses festivals at one end and busking at the other end. Further research is advised on how outdoor venues shape visitors' experiences (Oakes and Warnaby, 2011). Burland and Pitts (2012) explored the indoor venue experience of a jazz club in Oxford, and underlined the importance of intimacy that indoor venues have for audiences, as well as a connection felt with other listeners and the performers. High expectations of audience members in the indoor venue context were highlighted (Burland and Pitts, 2012).

An important term in the festival context is *festivalscape*, which refers to a festival's programme, infrastructure, and information, among others (Grappi and Montanari,

2011; Lee et al. 2008). Kruger and Saayman (2017) identified three *festivalscape* factors at the Cape Town International Jazz Festival, of which 'artist selection' was the most important, followed by 'accessibility and ambience', and 'visual and sound interpretation' (2017:218).

The literature on the market segmentation of jazz audiences has suggested that there are different types of jazz festival attendees according to their motives. Williams and Saayman (2013) identified three types of jazz visitors at the Cape Town International Jazz festival: 'Jazz lovers', who were searching for an extraordinary jazz experience; 'Escapists', labelled as accompanying persons; and 'Cultural seekers', who were searching for novel and new jazz experiences (2013:193). No significant differences were found between different types of residents and these three types of attendees. Audience segmentation research based on participants' knowledge of different jazz styles identified festival visitors as great jazz connoisseurs, visitors with some knowledge of jazz more acquainted with popular jazz genres, and visitors unfamiliar with jazz (Pérez et al., 2021). Kruger and Saayman (2017) suggested that jazz festival organisers should offer a varied programme content, as this helps lesser-known artists become more visible to attract different types of audiences and properly market their target group. Moreover, McKay (2018) analysed the relationship between diversifying programmes and renewing festival audiences with reference to the Montreux jazz festival, where pop music was included as part of the programme. However, expanding audiences involves widening the set of needs that have to be considered, and in this context, accessibility plays a significant role, as it increases motivation and opportunity for audience

attendance (Kemp and Poole, 2016). Therefore, marketing practices should consider this for their audience development plans (Kemp and Poole, 2016).

Festival literature in regards to the audiences' residence area reveals that loyalty is commonly placed in the research focus. In this line, Chang et al. (2014) evaluated loyalty in terms of likelihood of returning to the annual heritage (Tulip) festival in Michigan, and indicated that local residents who were highly satisfied with the festival were also likely to return to the festival unlike the tourists. The satisfaction with the festival of both groups resulted in positive correlation with their psychological involvement with the festival. Conversely, tourists showed greater level of loyalty to the film festival in Chile than the local visitors which is why researchers suggest the festivals' organisers to understand local residents' expectations to a greater extent and to ensure their satisfaction. This is related to the fact that locals are the closest to the festival and could most easily attend it in case non-locals are prevented from coming (Báez-Montenegro and Devesa-Fernández, 2017). Repeat visitors from outside of the festival's place turned out to be more satisfied and loyal to the National Cherry Blossom Festival in Washington, and demonstrated higher emotional values than the non-local first-time visitors (Deng and Pierskalla, 2011). The economic aspect was as well explored among locals and non-locals. For example, Thrane (2002) argue how greater distance from the jazz festival in Norway positively correlates with higher expenditures at the festival, which confirms the findings of Herrero et al. (2012) who showed higher WTP (willingness to pay) among tourists than the locals in a Spanish festival context at a classical music festival. Another Spanish case that represents research on local versus non-local differences by Richards (2007) held in Barcelona, explains how authenticity is interpreted where the former

linked it to the cultural and social aspect, while the latter to experience and enjoyment of the event. Sirianni and Sabbagh (2020) focused on locals' perceptions of a festival and highlighted relationships among their personal well-being and the sense of community and social benefits in the Spanish town Cáceres. Formica and Uysal (1996) draw differences among visitors and local residents at Umbria Jazz Festival and encountered that tourists gave more importance to entertainment while local residents to the socialisation aspect.

Place and the socio-spatial aspect have been at the centre of research in relation to festival authenticity. Wang (1999) explained how both intrapersonal and interpersonal relationships influence authenticity. Rickly-Boyd (2013) highlighted the relationship between place and authenticity, since audiences react emotionally to the places where jazz festivals are held. Szmigin et al. (2017) noted that authenticity is created among audience members in music festivals and emphasised the importance of the socio-spatial aspect in so doing.

The literature review reveals that jazz festivals have been studied from different perspectives, especially by analysing their various impacts and from a marketing point of view. However, the audience experience as a holistic phenomenon has been explored to a lesser extent. One of the challenges involved in studying the audience experience is measuring it. Radbourne et al. (2009) developed a tool to measure the quality of the audience experience in the performing arts through four Indicators (Knowledge, Authenticity, Risk and Collective Engagement) which form part of the Audience Experience Survey. They relied on these to analyse how audiences relate to an event in a cognitive, emotional, and social way.

This study uses a form of the Audience Experience Survey (Radbourne et al., 2009) that has been adapted to the jazz festival context by adding some new items. Section 3 below expands on this information.

4.3 Methodology

4.3.1 Instrument

A questionnaire was created to meet the aim of this study, which involved adapting the Audience Experience Survey for the performing arts proposed by Radbourne et al. (2009) to the jazz festival context. This entailed combining it with additional questions and statements to further explore the audience experience. The questionnaire contains Likert scale statements as well as open-ended and socio-demographic questions.

As originally devised by Radbourne et al. (2009), the Audience Experience Survey started with two open-ended questions regarding the name of the performance and the expectations of it. It was adapted to the concerts performed at the Heineken Jazzaldia Festival. Three groups of Likert scale statements were organised into three dimensions: *Familiarity*, *Importance* and *Satisfaction*, which were changed to ensure relevance to live music and the music festival context. *Familiarity* measured the participants' level of acquaintance with festivals and their motivation to attend. One item in the *Familiarity* dimension was modified and new ones were added. The *Importance* dimension acknowledged the value that participants gave to live music events in general, while the *Satisfaction* dimension measured participants' satisfaction with the concert they attended.

The *Importance* and *Satisfaction* dimensions form what is known as the Audience Experience Index, which captures four different indicators of the concerts attended at the festival: *Knowledge*, *Authenticity*, *Collective Engagement*, and *Risk*. Each dimension

comprises 8 items, two for each indicator. Each item is numbered by the initial of the dimension group and item number (Table I). *Knowledge* concerns the audience's cognitive stimulation and the concert as an opportunity for learning. From the viewpoint of the audience experience, knowledge influences it by enabling a better understanding of the performance spectators are experiencing (Kawashima, 2006; Radbourne et al., 2009). In addition, it was highlighted in the literature review how knowledge is also a relevant variable for segmentation (Pérez et al., 2021; Williams and Saayman, 2013). *Authenticity* refers to the plausibility the performance has for the audience and their emotional response to it. It is associated with greater positive experiences of the event. As Szmigin et al. (2017) suggest, socio-spatial aspect of authenticity is relevant in the music festival context as well. The discussion section will expand on this aspect based on the results. Collective Engagement relates to "the audience member's sense of being engaged with the performer(s) and the other audience members and/or with discussions before or after the performance" (Radbourne et al., 2009:21). Formica and Uysal (1996) emphasized the importance of the socialization aspect for local residents. *Risk* measures the emotional and economic extent to which audiences are prepared for the performance. It seems that non-locals are more likely to take risk to a greater extent as they have greater expenditures (Thrane, 2002; Herrero et al., 2012).

Socio-demographic questions regarding age, gender, occupation, and the highest formal education degree obtained were adapted from the Audience Experience Survey (Radbourne et al., 2009). An additional question was included concerning the participants' area of residence. An additional response option was also inserted in the question about gender in order to use inclusive language (male, female, and other).

Finally, another open-ended question was added regarding the festival’s aspects that participants considered to be the best.

Prior to conducting the fieldwork, the adapted questionnaire was verified by two external researchers: one of the co-authors of the original Audience Experience Survey and an additional performing arts audience researcher. The survey was then translated by the authors of this paper, who are experienced in English to Spanish translations and vice versa. Prior to the administration of the questionnaire at the Heineken Jazzaldia Festival, a pretest was conducted at the Getxo Jazz Festival (Basque Country, Spain) in July 2019 to verify the audience’s understanding of the questionnaire. Upon completion of the pretest, some modifications were introduced, and two additional researchers were asked to review the linguistic (Spanish) and cultural (music festival) adaptation of the survey to prepare the final version for the Heineken Jazzaldia Festival (Table I). The final version administered to audiences did not contain any of the dimension names (*Familiarity, Importance, Satisfaction*) and indicators (*Knowledge, Authenticity, Collective Engagement, and Risk*) provided in Table I. Nevertheless, these names have been included in Table I to enhance understanding of the measurement tool.

Table I. Heineken Jazzaldia 2019 questionnaire: open-ended questions and groups of statements

1. Name the concert you have attended
2. Prior to attending, what were your expectations about this concert?
3. Please rate your agreement with the following statements (from 1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree, or Do not know/Does not apply):

<i>Familiarity</i>	
F1.	I attend as many concerts at Heineken Jazzaldia Festival as possible.
F2.	I really like the selection of artists at this festival.
F3.	I really like the selection of artists at this venue (stage).
F4.	I really like the work of this particular musician/musical group.

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- F5. I really like how the festival has been organised.
 - F6. I really like this type of music festival.
 - F7. I would like to go to this type of music festival more often.
 - F8. I have been looking forward to coming to this music Festival.
 - F9. I have been looking forward to attending this festival in the company of friends and/or family.
 - F10. I have been looking forward to attending this festival in the company of other people who are interested in this type of music.
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4. Please rate the importance of the following aspects to your experience at MUSICAL EVENTS IN GENERAL (from 1 = not at all important to 5 = very important, or Do not know/Does not apply), taking into account other types of music performances you have attended prior to this Festival:

Importance

Knowledge	I1.	Notes about the performance and the work of the artists are included in the programme.
Risk	I2.	The venue/arts centre/festival presents my preferred type of shows.
Authenticity	I3.	The performance matches expectations from the promotional description.
Collective	I4.	Audiences know there are established rules for audience behaviour (e.g., When to clap, no speaking during the concert).
Engagement	I5.	The musicians/musical groups show technical skills and understanding of the work.
Authenticity	I6.	I have previously seen or heard this work (production), or accessed a preview on the Web.
Risk	I7.	When I attend a concert, I want to be challenged to think differently about ideas and issues presented in the show.
Knowledge	I8.	Audience members have the opportunity to discuss the performance with others at some point after the show.
Collective		
Engagement		

5. Please rate your agreement with the following statements (from 1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree, or Do not know/Does not apply):

Satisfaction

Risk	S1.	The quality of the concert was worth the cost of attendance (ticket, transport, parking, personal).
Authenticity	S2.	The reputation of the performers was matched by the quality of the performance.
Knowledge	S3.	I learned something new from this performance.
Knowledge	S4.	My enjoyment or appreciation of jazz increased from this performance.
Authenticity	S5.	The best performers were those who communicated directly with the audience.
Collective	S6.	Other members of the audience seemed to have a similar response to the performance as I did.
Engagement	S7.	I felt enthusiastic and excited at moments during the concert.
Risk	S8.	Attending this live performance with other people increased my understanding of how audiences and performers interact.
Collective		
Engagement		

6. What aspects of the Heineken Jazzaldia did you like the most?

4.3.2 Sample

Convenience sampling was chosen, as it is frequently used in event research (Shipway et al., 2012). The unknown population proportions suggest a conservative response format, where 50 percent will positively respond to questions, and 50 percent negatively

(Aaker et al, 2019; Akis et al, 1996). The sampling error was 5 percent, with a confidence level of 95 percent.

Aaker et al. (2019) suggested that error is determined by the sample, as the total population size is independent of sample size. Our sampling design was cross-sectional. Some 431 questionnaires were obtained from participants of various age groups and genders. Missing data (including the 'does not apply/do not know' field) affected the total number of valid questionnaires, as 25 participants left more than 30% of the fields blank. Finally, 406 valid questionnaires were collected throughout the festival. Statistical significance was accepted at a 0.05 confidence level, and the statistical error of 4.8 percent. Categorical variable data are shown in Table II.

According to the Jazzaldia webpage (jazzaldia.eus, August 2021), the total number of spectators in 2019 was 168,000. For a population above 100,000 (N) including the level of confidence of 95% and margin of error of 5%, 384 participants are seen as representative (Krejcie and Morgan, 1970). The number of valid questionnaires obtained in this study (n=406) is, therefore, larger than required.

Table II. Categorical variables

Categorical variables	Number of participants	% Sample participants
Gender		
Male	182	45.5
Female	209	52.3
Other	7	1.8
Missing data	6	
Age Group		
Under 30	65	16.3
31 to 40	67	16.8
41 to 50	111	27.8
51 to 60	103	25.8
61+	54	13.5
Missing data	6	
Occupation		
Employed	304	76.2
Student	29	7.3
Retired	40	10.0
Other	20	5.0
Working and studying	4	1.0
Missing data	7	

Education -highest level attained-		
Primary school	14	3.5
Secondary school	65	16.3
Bachelor's degree	219	54.8
Master's degree or PhD	102	25.5
Missing data	6	
Expectations about the concert		
No expectations	80	20.3
High expectations	134	34.0
Very high expectations	71	18.0
Curiosity/Enjoyment/Having new experiences/Spontaneity/Ordinary/Normal	109	27.7
Missing data	12	
Area of residence		
San Sebastián	119	29.8
Basque Country (Álava, Vizcaya, and Guipúzcoa)	75	18.8
Spain (outside the Basque Country)	178	44.5
Outside Spain	28	7.0
Missing data	6	
Admission		
Paid admission to concerts	213	54.3
Free admission to concerts	179	45.7
Missing data	14	
Type of venue		
Indoor venue concerts	307	78.3
Outdoor venue concerts	85	21.7
Missing data	14	

4.3.3 Data collection

The fieldwork at the Heineken Jazzaldia Festival was carried out during each day of the festival, from 24th to 28th July 2019. Six researchers were placed opposite the four outdoor stages (Green Heineken Stage, Heineken Terrace, Frigo Space, Coca-Cola Space) and the four indoor stages (Victoria Eugenia Theatre, Victoria Eugenia Club inside the Victoria Eugenia Theatre, Kursaal Auditorium, The San Telmo Museum- Fundación SGAE Space), where they administered the questionnaire. It was decided to consider the San Telmo Museum stage as an indoor venue, as it was inside the museum building under a marquee in a small open space, as opposed to the uncovered open-air stages that were near the sea, with a diverse audience flow. The questionnaires were distributed during the day until 9pm and were completed by participants themselves. Trying to obtain questionnaire responses from festival goers after the late-night concerts organised at

outdoor venues would have been made difficult due to highly diminished visibility. Another obstacle was the weather. There were rainstorms for three days and some festival concerts were cancelled. The researchers could therefore only use porch roof sections in front of the indoor concert halls.

4.3.4 Data analysis

To conduct a statistical analysis of the responses to the first open-ended question (participants' expectations of the concert), the answers were coded into 'mutually exclusive' categories, as advised by Kent (2015:58). The aim was to use a gradual semantic structure to facilitate the analysis and comparison with participants' area of residence. Following the recommended procedure, a set of 50 surveys was taken into account to create the response category framework (Kent, 2015). Afterwards, each new category analysed was added to the already formed category or a new one was created if necessary. Three groups were formed according to the participants' answers: 1. no expectations, 2. high expectations and, 3. very high expectations. A criterion to lexically define these three groups was the use of the exact words 'no', 'high', and 'very high'. The 'no expectations' group included 50 participants who reported that they did not know the performer before the concert. Participants who answered that they trusted the organisers, that someone had recommended a band to them, or that they liked this type of music were excluded from the analysis, as it was not clear if they had expectations and if so, what type or level of expectations these were. We understood that this was part of their motivation to attend. Participants who did not know the performer but reported that they always have high expectations of Heineken Jazzaldia Festival were placed in the high expectations group, as the word 'high' was explicitly stated in their answer. The high expectations group also included answers that referred to 'good' or

'great' expectations. The very high expectations group included answers such as 'really high', 'huge', 'very high', 'the greatest' expectations. Around 28% of participants reported that their expectations were linked to 'curiosity', 'enjoyment', 'having new experiences', 'spontaneity', and they had 'ordinary' or 'normal' expectations, as shown in Table II. As these answers did not fit the first three no/high/very high expectations either semantically or in terms of degree, they have been excluded from the analysis in section 4.4.2.1.

Regarding the area of residence (Table II), approximately 7% of the sample included residents outside Spain. This group was excluded from the analysis in section 4 due to the significantly smaller number of participants and the heterogeneity of the group (28 participants from 12 countries and 3 continents) in comparison with other residence area groups.

The exclusion of data on the residence area and the expectation groups for statistical analysis purposes led to a total of 263 participants in the analysis of these two variables (sub-section 4.4.2.1). This resulted from discarding missing data (blank answers). The comparison of the residence area and the venue setting (indoor versus outdoor) yielded a total of 358 participants who were included in the analysis (4.4.2.2 section), after discarding blank answers. Finally, the analysis of the residence area and the festival's best aspects covered a total of 275 participants, after excluding blank answers.

IBM SPSS Statistics 26 was used to conduct the One-way Anova and the Chi square tests. One-way Anova was applied to test the relationship between the residence area and the three groups of statements (*Familiarity*, *Importance* and *Satisfaction*). Chi square tests were applied to test if there was a significant relationship between participants'

residence area and two categorical variables: first, participants' concert expectations and, second, their preference for a venue setting (indoor versus outdoor). A Cramer's V test was applied to evaluate the strength of association, where the maximum possible value is 1, as there are more than two categories within categorical variables (Field, 2013).

The formulation of the second open-ended question on the festival's best aspects and the way the answers were obtained did not facilitate a quantitative analysis, since the total number of aspects mentioned in the answers exceeded the number of participants who responded to this question. Nevertheless, some aspects were found to be repeated. We chose In Vivo coding, one of the most common qualitative coding methods (Miles et al., 2014). As advised, the same descriptions repeated by participants helped to identify a coding pattern.

The findings from each analysis are reported and described in the following section.

4.4 Results

The findings are organised in the following three sub-sections. The first section informs on both significant and non-significant differences obtained from the One-way Anova analysis regarding participants' area of residence and the items from *Familiarity*, *Importance* and *Satisfaction* dimensions, including the four Indicators (*Knowledge*, *Authenticity*, *Risk* and *Collective Engagement*). This section further expands information on significant differences only. The second sub-section includes the results from the Chi square tests. As two categorical variables (concerts' expectations and venue setting) were analysed in relation to participants' area of residence, the second subsection comprises two parts. The last section is based on the qualitative analysis of the festival's best aspects according to participants' opinions.

4.4.1 Area of residence and audience experience

One-way Anova tests were conducted to explore whether and how each item in the *Familiarity, Importance, and Satisfaction* groups varied according to participants' areas of residence. The responses were classified into three groups: 1. San Sebastian area, 2. Basque Country (excluding San Sebastian) and 3. Spain (excluding the Basque Country). Table III reflects significant and non-significant differences obtained.

Table III. Audience experience according to participants' residence area: One way ANOVA (significant and non-significant differences)

	F(df)	p-value
F1. I attend as many concerts at Heineken Jazzaldia festival as possible.	F(2,363)=4,686	0,010*
F2. I really like the selection of artists at this Festival.	F(2,365)=0,086	0,917
F3. I really like the selection of artists at this venue (stage).	F(2,355)=1,078	0,341
F4. I really like the work of this particular musician/band.	F(2,355)=3,886	0,021*
F5. I really like how the Festival has been organised.	F(2,365)=0,368	0,692
F6. I really like this type of music festival.	F(2,367)=3,282	0,039*
F7. I would like to go to this type of music festival more often.	F(2,364)=2,887	0,057
F8. I have been looking forward to coming to this music festival.	F(2,359)=8,239	0,000**
F9. I have been looking forward to attending this festival in the company of friends and /or family.	F(2,359)=2,332	0,099
F10. I have been looking forward to attending this festival in the company of other people who are interested in this type of music.	F(2,353)=2,496	0,084
I1. Notes about the performance and the work of the artists are included in the programme.	F(2,360)=0,803	0,449
I2. The venue/arts centre/festival presents my preferred type of shows.	F(2,356)=0,708	0,493
I3. The performance matches expectations from the promotional description.	F(2,355)=1,123	0,327
I4. Audiences know there are established rules for audience behavior (eg. When to clap, no speaking during the concert).	F(2,354)=2,044	0,131
I5. The musicians/musical groups show technical skill and understanding of the work.	F(2,359)=0,438	0,646
I6. I have previously seen or heard this work (production), or accessed a preview on the Web.	F(2,332)=2,239	0,108
I7. When I attend a concert I want to be challenged to think differently about ideas and issues presented in the show.	F(2,350)=2,382	0,094
I8. Audience members have the opportunity to discuss the performance with others some time after the show.	F(2,341)=1,068	0,345
S1. The quality of the concert was worth the cost of attendance (ticket, transport, parking, personal).	F(2,347)=0,097	0,907
S2. The reputation of the performers was matched by the quality of the performance.	F(2,346)=4,626	0,010*
S3. I learned something new from this performance.	F(2,356)=1,079	0,341
S4. My enjoyment or appreciation of Jazz increased from this performance.	F(2,353)=0,962	0,383
S5. The best performers were those who communicated directly with the audience.	F(2,347)=4,477	0,012*
S6. Other members of the audience seemed to have a similar response to the performance as I did.	F(2,341)=2,078	0,127
S7. I felt enthusiastic and excited at moments during the concert.	F(2,367)=3,693	0,026*
S8. Attending this live performance with other people increased my understanding of how audiences and performers interact.	F(2,350)=0,141	0,869

Note. * $p < .05$. ** $p < 0.001$

The following sections outline the significant differences between participants from different residence areas and refer to the *Familiarity* and *Satisfaction* dimensions only, given that no significant differences were encountered regarding the *Importance* dimension. The post hoc tests showed where the significant relationship lay.

F1. There were more participants from Spain ($M=3.99$, $SE=0.07$) who reported that they attended as many concerts at the Heineken Jazzaldia Festival as possible than participants resident in the Basque Country ($M=3.57$, $SE=0.13$). This relationship $F(2,363)=4,686$ was significant at $p=0.010$, based on $n=365$.

F4. More participants from the Basque Country ($M=4.36$, $SE=0.11$) and Spain ($M=4.21$, $SE=0.07$) reported that they really liked the work of a particular musician or band whose concert they attended than participants from San Sebastian ($M=3.97$, $SE=0.09$). This relationship $F(2,355)=3,886$ was significant at $p=0.021$, based on $n=357$.

F6. Participants who were resident in Spain ($M=4.62$, $SE=0.05$) expressed that they liked this type of music festival more than San Sebastian participants ($M=4.41$, $SE=0.07$). This relationship $F(2,367)=3,282$ was significant at $p=0.039$, based on $n=369$.

F8. Participants from Spain ($M=4.55$, $SE=0.06$) had been looking forward to coming to the music festival more than participants from San Sebastian ($M=4.21$, $SE=0.08$) and the Basque Country ($M=4.22$, $SE=0.08$). This relationship $F(2,359)=8,239$ was significant at $p=0.000$, based on $n=361$.

S2. San Sebastian participants ($M=4.22$, $SE=0.07$) considered that the reputation of the artists was less matched to the quality of the concert than the other residents from the Basque Country ($M=4.47$, $SE=0.10$) and the ones from the rest of Spain ($M=4.51$, $SE=0.06$). This relationship $F(2,346)=4,626$ was significant at $p=0.010$, based on $n=348$.

S5. The participants from San Sebastian (M=4.14, SE=0.09) believed that the best artists were those who interacted with the audience more strongly than participants from Spain (M=3.80, SE=0.08). This relationship $F(2,347)=4,477$ was significant at $p=0.012$, based on $n=349$.

S7. Participants from the rest of Spain (M=4.35, S=0.06) were more enthusiastic and excited during the concerts than San Sebastian participants (M=4.08, S=0.08). This relationship $F(2,367)=3,693$ was significant at $p=0.026$, based on $n=369$.

4.4.2 Area of residence versus expectations and venue setting

4.4.2.1 Area of residence versus concert expectations

There was a significant association between participants' area of residence (San Sebastian, Basque Country, Spain) and whether they attended a concert without any expectations, or had high or very high expectations, $\chi^2 = 12.59$, $p=0.013$.

Cramer's V statistic was 0.155, and the p-value was 0.013 for the data collected, showing that the strength of the relationship was significant, and that while there was some association between the two variables, they were not strongly associated.

As shown in Table IV, within the expectations' category, there was a higher percentage of participants from Spain (outside of the Basque Country) who had high or very high expectations prior to the concert than participants from San Sebastian and the Basque Country. Therefore, it seems that expectations rose as the distance of the participants' residence area from the festival increased. Nevertheless, post-hoc test showed a significant difference (Table IV, p-value in bold) among local residents with no expectations prior to the concerts. In contrast, most participants from the Basque

Country (other than San Sebastian) and Spain had high expectations, while there were lower percentages with either no expectations or very high expectations.

Table IV. Area of residence versus expectations: Chi-square and cross-tabulation results

Pearson Chi-Square	df	p-value	Phi	Cramer's V	Number of Valid Cases
12,588	4	,013	,219	,155	263

		San Sebastian	Basque Country	Spain	Total %within expectations
No expectations	% within expectations	45.9%	13.5%	40.5%	100.0%
	% within area of residence	41.5%	17.2%	24.4%	
	Post-hoc p-value after Bonferroni correction	,00137	,03573	,19360	
High expectations	% within expectations	25.6%	23.2%	51.2%	100.0%
	% within area of residence	39.0%	50.0%	52.0%	
	Post-hoc p-value after Bonferroni correction	,05743	,68916	,16151	
Very high expectations	% within expectations	25.0%	29.7%	45.3%	100.0%
	% within area of residence	19.5%	32.8%	23.6%	
	Post-hoc p-value after Bonferroni correction	,23014	,08913	,76418	
Total	% within area of residence	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

4.4.2.2 Area of residence versus venue setting

There was a highly significant relationship between the participants' area of residence (San Sebastian, Basque Country, Spain) and whether they attended a concert in an outdoor versus an indoor venue, $\chi^2 = 46,110$, $p=0,000$.

Cramer's V statistic was 0,359, and the p-value was highly significant $p=0,000$, which indicates a medium strength of association. As it can be seen in Table V (p-value in bold), significant differences appeared in residents from Spain who had the highest indoor venue attendance

within the area of residence category. The Basque Country group had higher indoor venue attendance in comparison with San Sebastian participants. Regarding the venue setting variable, significant differences showed that San Sebastian participants favoured outdoor settings more than groups of participants from the Basque Country and the rest of Spain.

Table V. Area of residence area versus venue setting: Chi-square and cross-tabulation results

Pearson Chi-Square	df	p-value	Phi	Cramer's V	Number of Valid Cases
46,110	2	,000	,359	,359	358
			Indoor venue	Outdoor venue	Total % within area of residence area
San Sebastián	% within area of residence	57.1%	42.9%	100.0%	
	% within venue setting	23.0%	60.0%		
	Post-hoc p-value after Bonferroni correction	,00000	,00000		
Basque Country	% within area of residence	76.4%	23.6%	100.0%	
	% within venue setting	19.8%	21.3%		
	Post-hoc p-value after Bonferroni correction	,76417	,76417		
Spain	% within area of residence	91.4%	8.6%	100.0%	
	% within venue setting	57.2%	18.8%		
	Post-hoc p-value after Bonferroni correction	,00000	,00000		
Total	% within venue setting	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	

4.4.3 Festival's best aspects

The answers to the open-ended question on the festival's best aspects were categorised into the following thematic groups for the analysis: music aspect (music diversity, performers, and programme), concert stages, place (city, surroundings), atmosphere,

free-admission concerts, and organisation. Some of the participants mentioned only one aspect, while others referred to two or more. Firstly, some findings related to the thematic groups analysed will be presented below, according to participants' area of residence; and secondly, the aspect mentioned the most and the least by each residence group will be reported.

The music aspect was the broadest one and accounted for almost half of all the responses collected. The most-mentioned topic within the music aspect was that the festival offered a diversified and varied programme. The wide range of styles and the quality of both unknown and familiar bands were highly appreciated.

Participants from San Sebastian mentioned the presence of female musicians and the opportunity given to music students and local bands such as *Nogen* to perform, which the younger population enjoyed. *Txikijazz* (jazz programme for children) was mentioned several times as the best festival's aspect by San Sebastian participants and once by one participant from the Basque Country.

It was found that the participants from Spain (other than from the Basque Country) mentioned music aspects more often than the two other groups. They described the artists who were appearing as being among the best in the field. They emphasised the high standard of most the performers and bands, the commitment that artists showed to their performance, and the great quality of the programme content. These participants also praised the inclusion of avant-garde jazz, the varied programme, and showed an appreciation of the strictly jazz part of the programme.

Participants from the Basque Country outside of San Sebastian, apart from stressing diversity and the excellence of performers, noted the presence of music students and

the quality of the lesser-known musicians. They enjoyed the opportunity to discover new talent and old unfamiliar musicians as well as Basque performers.

After music content, the most commonly mentioned aspect was the stages at the festival. Participants from the Basque Country and Spain considered these to be the best trait of the festival more than San Sebastian participants. In general, participants appreciated the settings where the stages were located (indoor versus outdoor), the number and diversity of stages, the performances on the beach, in the open-air, the proximity between stages, and accessibility to the various stages. Basque Country and Spain participants believed that the best stages were Plaza Trinidad, Green Heineken stage, Victoria Eugenia Theatre, Coca-Cola stage, Kursaal, and San Telmo Museum.

Free-admission concerts were more frequently mentioned by Basque Country residents and less mentioned by the group coming from other parts of Spain. Participants highlighted that concerts were diverse, free, and held in the open air; they also noted the opportunity to listen to good musicians for free, to enjoy free concerts on the beach, the quality of the performances, the fact most concerts were free of charge, the opportunity to get to know new bands at no cost, free admission as a method of bringing culture closer to people, and the festival's openness to the city's residents due to free-admission concerts.

Ambience was primarily mentioned by San Sebastian participants and less frequently noted by the Spanish group of participants as the festival's best aspect. In general, the main points made referred to the festival's and the city's atmosphere, the atmosphere at the different stages, and the fact that performances were outdoors.

The location was mentioned by residents in San Sebastian and by the group of participants from Spain (other than the Basque Country). Participants from other areas of Spain also highlighted the beauty of San Sebastian, its natural, cultural, and artistic heritage, and the successful integration of the festival into the city. In general terms, the three groups mentioned the surroundings, being in the open air, the beach stages, and the locations near the sea.

Organisation was the most mentioned aspect by the group of participants from Spain. All three groups mentioned that the organisation of the event was good or very good. Several participants regarded customer care, hospitality, the festival's poster, punctuality, and the festival's identity as the most outstanding characteristics. Finally, there was a smaller number of participants in each group of residents who liked everything about the festival and described it as spectacular and highly successful.

Regarding the San Sebastian group, the festival's music was the most frequently mentioned topic. Music diversity and bands were highlighted with similar frequency. The stages and the atmosphere were as frequently mentioned as they were by the other two subgroups within the music aspect, music diversity and performers. The fourth best aspect for the San Sebastian group was the location, the organisation being the fifth.

Concerning participants from the Basque Country, music was the most mentioned aspect. Music diversity was more frequently mentioned than the performers. Stages were the second most outstanding aspect for the participants from the Basque Country, followed by free-admission concerts, ambience, and organisation, in this order.

The music aspect was the most frequently mentioned by the group of participants from other areas in Spain. They noted that they had enjoyed the diversity in music more than

the bands themselves, as was the case for the Basque Country group. The second most remarkable aspect for this group were the stages, followed by the organisation, location, and free-admission concerts.

4.5 Discussion

The main findings from the analysis suggest that being a resident of an area that was at a greater distance from the festival's location was related to having higher expectations about the concerts, to having stronger motivation to attend the festival, to attending indoor concerts, and to giving more importance to the music diversity aspect (regarded as the most outstanding feature of the festival) in comparison with local residents' preferences. Unlike some previous research (Burland and Pitts, 2012), we identified a certain number of participants who did not have any expectations prior to concerts. This may be observed through the festival context itself as it offers a great number of artists and concerts, and an opportunity to discover new artists. Therefore, we could expect to some extent that some concerts are not familiar to one part of the audience. What is interesting and novel here is that we identified that not having expectations is rather related to local residents than the ones from the rest of Spain. Moreover, as significant differences indicate greater presence of non-locals in the indoor venues, our findings can be interesting to the festival's organisers, especially if they are interested in attracting locals to jazz musicians who perform indoors. We add to the body of knowledge that tourists were more psychologically engaged with the festival in terms of their expectations, motivation and emotions experienced at the festival than the locals. Regarding the festival's best aspects, non-local residents prioritised music diversity as the festival's best aspect, then stages which are followed by artists, organisation, etc.,

while the locals gave equal level of importance to music diversity, performers, stages, and atmosphere. This result adds to the knowledge area in the Spanish festival context, as some of the previous research regarding differences in experiences among locals and non-locals in a festival context, delved into economic aspect, (Herrero et al., 2012), authenticity (Richards, 2007), and subjective well-being of local residents and their support for future festivals (Sirianni and Sabbagh, 2020). The diverse music styles in the programme were the most outstanding trait of the festival: a variety of (jazz) styles, music that catered for different tastes and type of audiences. The fact that one part of the programme did not require having any special jazz knowledge, while others were strictly for jazz connoisseurs, was recognised and highly appreciated by participants. This view of diversity is in line with jazz festival's richness in styles found by Laver (2015). Whereas bands and the quality of the performances used to be the most important factor for jazz festival visitors (Kruger and Saayman, 2017), in this case music diversity prevailed over the choice of performers included in the programme.

Participants from outside of the Basque Country were more highly motivated to attend the festival and enjoyed the performance of a particular band more than local participants. This greater preference for a particular jazz band could be related to the fact that non-local participants had to make a greater effort to attend the festival in terms of time, travel organisation and financial resources.

It was additionally found that non-local participants presented lower emotional Risk (Radbourne et al., 2009), as they showed greater enthusiasm during the concerts. Regarding the Authenticity indicator (Radbourne et al., 2009), participants from the Basque Country and from other parts of Spain considered the quality of the

performances to be matched with the musicians' reputation to a greater extent than San Sebastian participants.

Local participants attended outdoor venue concerts more often, and they considered the atmosphere and free admission to be the festival's best characteristics more frequently than participants from the rest of Spain. It is noteworthy that outdoor venue settings were more flexible in terms of genres (e.g., rock and pop) than indoor venue settings at the festival. An example that illustrates this was a concert by the band *Nogen*, held at an outdoor venue setting, which was mentioned by local participants as one of the most outstanding aspects of the festival. This is consistent with the literature that has shown how diverse programme offerings may attract new audiences to jazz festivals (McKay, 2018); or, in this case, visitors who were not strictly jazz fans.

Furthermore, the fact that local residents showed higher agreement that the best performers were those who directly interacted with the audience in comparison with participants from Spain was in line with the Authenticity indicator (Radbourne et al., 2009).

Stages, venues, and places where the concerts were held were the second most important factor in terms of the audience's experience, following the music aspect. As local participants had a greater preference for outdoor venue settings, the stages they referred to were frequently open-air and outdoor venues, concerts on the beach, and many places to listen to live music on the street, as well as their proximity and accessibility. The findings related to outdoor settings at the festival were consistent with the three continuums established by Oakes and Warnaby (2011). People could move from one stage to the other, experience live music more spontaneously than in managed

indoor venue settings. Apart from the Authenticity indicator previously related to concert settings, in terms of the believability of, and emotional relationship with performers, as explained by Radbourne et al. (2009), this study also encountered emotional attachment to the festival's setting. Through the participants' descriptions of the location (the beach, the city, and the venues) as the best aspect of the festival, the authenticity experienced extended beyond the concert setting to the overall festival's level, which suggests the importance of the socio-spatial aspect in the (jazz) music festival context (Rickly-Boyd, 2013; Szmigin et al., 2017).

While free admission concerts were important for all groups, they were more often mentioned by the Basque Country participants. This was welcomed by participants as a way of meeting new musicians and making the programme accessible to everyone. The importance of accessibility highlighted by Kemp and Poole (2016) was observed in the Heineken Jazzaldia Festival in that participants strongly emphasised the importance of having free-admission concerts and easy access to outdoor venues, especially near the beach, where some concerts were held.

As the Heineken Jazzaldia Festival offers a large number of concerts over several days, the fact that someone did not know the performer before the concert may not be the case for the same participant at another festival' concert.

The city of San Sebastián was recognised as the most outstanding feature of the festival by both San Sebastian and rest-of-Spain (non-Basque) participants. The festival's integration into the city, with some of its major locations becoming jazz venues, was assessed by the participants as an added value. It has been Jazzaldia's practice to incorporate the city's landscape into the festival from its early days, as the festival was

characterised by having outdoor venues from the very beginning (Barnés, 2007). This is also highly valued nowadays. The festival's influence on the city's image is one of the characteristics of jazz festivals (Bonneau and Parantika, 2016). In addition, it was particularly remarkable for participants that the festival was held outdoors, on the beach and near the sea, which was how they described the stages, and the extent to which visitors appreciated the beauty of the natural environment.

4.6 Final remarks

The purpose of this paper was to explore the audience experience at the Heineken Jazzaldia Festival in San Sebastian, considering how it varies depending on attendees' area of residence, taking into account their expectations, their preference for outdoor or indoor settings and what they regarded as the festival's best aspects.

As the findings showed, the area of residence played a role in audiences' expectations, motivation, and festival preferences. The limitations of this study are discussed below, along with recommendations for future research.

As explained in the Data analysis section, participants whose concert expectations were to enjoy the experience, to discover something new, or simply to satisfy their curiosity, were not selected for the quantitative analysis. Nevertheless, their views helped to understand the nature and intentions of festival goers and pave the way for future research.

Even though a total number of valid questionnaires (n=406) obtained in this study confirms the representativeness of data for a population above 100,000 (Krejcie and Morgan, 1970), some data that did not meet requirements for the quantitative and

qualitative analysis were excluded (see section 4.3.4). Therefore, the total number of participants' answers was reduced for the analysis. Hence, we acknowledge the need for future research to improve the representativeness of data.

We further acknowledge the use of convenience sampling as a limitation of this study. However, despite the Festival's location, the weather conditions, and the fact that we could not control for whether participants answered all the items, the total number of valid questionnaires is large which allowed us to carry out different types of tests. Therefore, we consider the results relevant to be considered.

Furthermore, we acknowledge the need to further investigate the experience of festival visitors in terms of the outdoor versus indoor settings and programme content according to their residence area, as this paper revealed a potential link between these groups. Moreover, we encourage further research that aims to embrace the social and environmental sustainability aspect of jazz festivals and events, since exploring preferences for outdoor versus indoor venue settings could greatly enhance the current understanding of the topic.

Finally, we believe these results may help festival organisers to acknowledge their audiences' motivations and preferences, and to improve their marketing and management strategies accordingly.

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